

IMI2 Project 802750 - FAIRplus
FAIRification of IMI and EFPIA data

**WP5 – Project management,
coordination, dissemination and
sustainability**

**D5.8 FAIRplus overview of the
scientific publications**

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1. Executive Summary

The IMI FAIRplus project has produced many physical ‘assets’, such as the FAIR Cookbook as well as developed processes such as the selection of datasets for FAIRification. In addition, much ‘knowledge’ obtained by the experts during the course of the project needs to be sustained. There has been an emphasis to ensure that publications, presentations and posters capture as much of the outputs of the IMI FAIRplus project as possible. Dissemination of these key assets, including the knowledge, is critical to ensure that FAIR becomes part of data culture in the long term. We expect some publications to be completed past the end of the project itself. Currently there are 11 publications in progress, with five published. The summary here only includes publications and examples of presentations by FAIRplus project partners. There have been other dissemination activities such as the FAIRplus innovation and SME Forum and webinars that are not listed here.

2. Introduction & Methods

To demonstrate the outcomes and impact of the FAIRplus project, WP5 together with other Work Packages have collected a list of publications related to the FAIRplus project, including

- 1) FAIRplus-led publications (including published, in-progress, and tentative publications)
- 2) publications co-funded by the project
- 3) publications that cited the FAIRplus project or the FAIR Cookbook
- 4) publications that mentioned the FAIRplus project, the FAIR Cookbook or the FAIRplus Fellowship programme
- 5) presentations or posters presented by FAIRplus project partners

During the FAIRplus project, the project partners also joined various conferences and webinars delivering talks on the FAIRplus project, its progress and resources developed. In the second part of the report, WP5 has collected a list of talks delivered by the FAIRplus project partners in different events.

3. Results

3.1 FAIRplus related Publications

FAIRplus-led publications

Table 1. List of FAIRplus-led publications, including published and in progress ones

Publication	Authors	Journal	Year
Status: published			
Selection of data sets for FAIRification in drug discovery and development: Which, why, and how? ¹	Alharbi, E., Gadiya, Y., Henderson, D., et al.	Drug Discovery Today	2022
The FAIR Cookbook - the essential resource by and for FAIR doers ²	Rocca-Serra, P., Gu, W., Ioannidis, V., et al. (WP2)	Scientific Data (Zenodo pre-print)	2022
FAIRification in action - a flexible framework to drive FAIRification ³	Welter, D., Juty, N., Rocca-Serra, P., et al. (WP2-3)	Scientific Data (Zenodo pre-print)	2022
The Translational Data Catalog - discoverable biomedical datasets ⁴	Welter, D., Rocca-Serra, P., Grouès, V., et al. (WP3)	Scientific Data (Zenodo pre-print)	2022
Experiment design driven FAIRification of omics data matrices, an exemplar ⁵	Rocca-Serra, P. & Sansone, S.	Scientific Data	2019
Status: in-progress			
A FAIR-Decide framework for pharmaceutical R&D: FAIR data cost-benefit	Alharbi, E., Juty, N., Goble, C.	Drug Discovery Today	Submitted - pre-print on Zenodo ⁶

¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1359644622001994?via%3Dihub>

² <https://zenodo.org/record/7156792#.Y1eoR-zMLtU>

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/7156792#.Y1eqxOzMLtV>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/7157285#.Y1etnOzMLtV>

⁵ <https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc6908569>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/6942268#.Y1-mquzP1qs>

assessment			
The FAIR dataset maturity model	Emam, I., Rocca-Serra, P. & Sansone, S. (WP2)	Scientific data	Draft ⁷
FAIR Wizard	Xu, F. & Burdett, T. (WP3)	Bioinformatics	Draft ready feedback in progress
FAIR tool discoverer	Navarrete, E., Capella, S., & Xu, F. (WP3)	Bioinformatics	Final draft with comments to be addressed
FAIR data in practice - our journey as a guide to you	Led by Sansone, S., Van Vlijmen, H. & Scollen, S. (all WPs)	Scientific data	Planned - <i>to be started when most of the other drafts are done</i>
Ten simple rules for aligning pharmaceutical R&D data with FAIR principles	Alharbi, E., Juty, N., Goble, C., Plasterer, T., Henderson, D., Gribbon, P., Gu, W. (WP1,2&3)		Started
Squads model/methodology, onboarding projects	Led by Juty, N. (WP2)	Scientific data	To be started
Example 1 of FAIRification*	Fellow(s) from pharmaceutical companies (WP4)	Scientific Data - <i>Data Descriptors or short Comment</i>	Tentative
Example 2 of FAIRification*	Fellow(s) from SME (WP4)	Scientific Data - <i>Data Descriptors or short Comment</i>	Tentative
Example 3 of FAIRification?*	Fellow(s) from academia (WP4)	Scientific Data - <i>Data Descriptors or short Comment</i>	Tentative
FAIR Sustainability	TBD Lynch, N., Williams-Jones, B., Scollen, S., Burdett, T.,	TBD	Tentative

⁷https://docs.google.com/document/d/1albbQYRieAFFqmdjO-NOExbyvT4wqoU3v1Qis_5aHPk/edit?pli=1#heading=h.hec0gidigf92

	Sansone, S., plus others		
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Publications co-funded by FAIRplus

Table 2. List of publications that are co-funded by the FAIRplus project

Publication	Authors	Journal	Year
The Challenge of the Effective Implementation of FAIR Principles in Biomedical Research ⁸	Parra-Calderón, C.L., Sanz, F. & McIntosh, L.D.	Methods of Information in Medicine	2021
Evaluating Behavioral and Linguistic Changes During Drug Treatment for Depression Using Tweets in Spanish: Pairwise Comparison Study ⁹	Leis, A., Ronzano, F., Mayer, M.A., Furlong, L.I. & Sanz, F.	Journal of Medical Internet Research	2020
Identifiers.org - Compact Identifier Services in the Cloud ¹⁰	Bernal-Llinares, M., Ferrer-Gómez, J., Juty, N., et al.	Bioinformatics	2020
FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles ¹¹	David, R., Mabile, L., Specht, A., et al.	Data Science Journal	2020
GPCRmd uncovers the dynamics of the 3D-GPCRome ¹²	Rodríguez-Espigares, I., Torrens-Fontanals, M., Tiemann, J.K.S., et al.	Nature Methods	2020
FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations ¹³	Jacobsen, A., de Miranda Azevedo, R., Juty, N., et al.	Data Intelligence	2020
Experiment design	Rocca-Serra, P. & Sansone, S.	Scientific Data	2019

⁸ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33618419/>

⁹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7775819/>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa864>

¹¹ <https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2020-032/>

¹² <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-020-0884-y>

¹³ <https://direct.mit.edu/dint/article/2/1-2/10/10017/FAIR-Principles-Interpretations-and-Implementation>

driven FAIRification of omics data matrices, an exemplar ¹⁴			
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Publications that cited the FAIRplus project or the FAIR Cookbook

Table 3. List of publications that cited the FAIRplus project, including the FAIRplus project, the FAIR Cookbook and the FAIRplus project funding

Publication	Authors	Journal	Year
FAIRplus project cited			
Exploring the current practices, costs and benefits of FAIR Implementation in pharmaceutical Research and Development: A Qualitative Interview Study ¹⁵	Alharbi, E., Skeva, R., Juty, N., Jay, C. & Goble, C.	Data Intelligence	2021
Cardiovascular RNA markers and artificial intelligence may improve COVID-19 outcome: a position paper from the EU-CardioRNA COST Action CA17129 ¹⁶	Badimon, L., Robinson, E.L., Jusic, A., et al.	Cardiovascular Research	2021
FAIR data sharing: The roles of common data elements and harmonization ¹⁷	Kush, R.D., Warzel, D., Kush, M.A., et al.	Journal of Biomedical Informatics	2020
The Data Tags Suite (DATS) model for discovering data access and use requirements ¹⁸	Alter G, Gonzalez-Beltran A, Ohno-Machado L, Rocca-Serra P.	Gigascience	2020

¹⁴ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-019-0286-0>

¹⁵ <https://direct.mit.edu/dint/article/3/4/507/107429/Exploring-the-Current-Practices-Costs-and-Benefits>

¹⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8083253/>

¹⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1532046420300496?via%3Dihub>

¹⁸ <https://academic.oup.com/gigascience/article/9/2/giz165/5730051>

The Need of Industry to Go FAIR ¹⁹	van Vlijmen, H., Mons, A., Waalkens, A. & Franke, W.	Data Intelligence	2020
Accelerating Chemical Tool Discovery by Academic Collaborative Models ²⁰	Stechmann, B. & Wolfgang, F.	In A. Stefaniu, A. Rasul, & G. Hussain (Eds.), Cheminformatics and its Applications. IntechOpen.	2020
Unique, Persistent, Resolvable: Identifiers as the Foundation of FAIR ²¹	Juty, N., Wimalaratne, S.M., Soiland-Reyes, S. & Kunze, J.	Data Intelligence	2020
FAIR Cookbook cited			
Work Programme for Health for 2023-2024 ²² (Cluster 1)	European Commission	European Commission	2022
Maximising investments in health research FAIR data for a coordinated COVID-19 response : workshop report ²³ (Appendix Table S2 & Appendix Text S5)	Maxwell, L.	Publication Office of the European Union	2022
FAIRplus project funding cited			
BioSamples database: FAIRer samples metadata to accelerate research data management ²⁴	Courtot, M., Gupta, D., Liyanage, I., Xu, F. & Burdett, T.	Nucleic Acids Research	2022
Flame: an open source framework for model development, hosting, and usage in	Pastor, M., Gómez-Tamayo, J.C. & Sanz, F.	Journal of Cheminformatics	2021

¹⁹ <https://direct.mit.edu/dint/article/2/1-2/276/10011/The-Need-of-Industry-to-Go-FAIR>

²⁰ <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/71022>

²¹ <https://direct.mit.edu/dint/article/2/1-2/30/9992/Unique-Persistent-Resolvable-Identifiers-as-the>

²² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/horizon-europe-work-programmes_en

²³ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f023acef-ba07-11ec-b6f4-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-254960712>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab1046>

production environments ²⁵			
Towards FAIR principles for research software ²⁶	Lamprecht, A., Garcia, L., Kuzak, M., et al.	Data Science	2020
Evaluating FAIR maturity through a scalable, automated, community-governed framework ²⁷	Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Sansone, S., et al.	Scientific data	2019
High-content live-cell multiplex screen for chemogenomic compound annotation based on nuclear morphology ²⁸	Tjaden, A., Giessmann, R.T., Knapp, S., et al.	STAR Protocols	2022

Publications that mentioned the FAIRplus project, the FAIR Cookbook or the FAIRplus Fellowship Programme

Table 4. List of publications that mentioned FAIRplus project, the FAIR Cookbook and the FAIRplus Fellowship Programme in the main text

Publication	Authors	Journal	Year
FAIR Genomes metadata schema promoting Next Generation Sequencing data reuse in Dutch healthcare and research ²⁹	van der Velde, K.J., Singh, G. & Kaliyaperumal, R.	Scientific Data	2022
Progress toward a comprehensive teaching approach to the FAIR data principles	Shanahan, H., Hoebelheinrich, N., Whyte, A.	Patterns	2021

²⁵ <https://jcheminf.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13321-021-00509-z>

²⁶ <https://www.research.ed.ac.uk/en/publications/towards-fair-principles-for-research-software>

²⁷ <https://research.vu.nl/en/publications/evaluating-fair-maturity-through-a-scalable-automated-community-g>

²⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9617200/>

²⁹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01265-x>

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Applying the FAIR principles to data in a hospital: challenges and opportunities in a pandemic ³¹	Queralt-Rosinach, N., Kaliyaperumal, R., Bernabé, C.H., et al.	medRxiv preprint	2021
How Patient Organizations Can Drive FAIR Data Efforts to Facilitate Research and Health Care: A Report of the Virtual Second International Meeting on Duchenne Data Sharing ³²	van Lin, N., Paliouras, G., Vroom, E., et al.	Journal of Neuromuscular Diseases	2021

Presentations or posters presented by FAIRplus project partners

Table 5. List of presentations and posters that are presented in meetings and conferences by the FAIRplus project partners

Publication	Authors	Meeting	Year
BPO: the Bioassay Protocol Ontology, a semantic approach to elevate the reusability of AMR-related drug discovery data ³³	Gadiya, Y., Arrazuria, R., Hansen, J.U., et al.	Poster displayed in ESCMID/ASM conference 2022, Dublin, Ireland	2022
FAIR Principle and FAIRness–focus on standards: brief overview of relevant activities ³⁴	Sansone, S.	Maximising investments in health research: FAIR data for a coordinated COVID-19 response. Workshop I, 11 October 2021	2021

³⁰ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666389921001720>

³¹ <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2021.08.13.21262023v2>

³² <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34334415/>

³³ https://zenodo.org/record/7187942#.Y1_Gh-zP1qs

³⁴

https://figshare.com/articles/presentation/FAIR_Data_for_COVID-19_Response_Workshop_I_The_FAIR_Principles_and_FAIRness_brief_overview_of_relevant_projects_and_activities_pdf/17143709/1

The Increasing Role of FAIR Data Practices in Biomedical Research ³⁵	Rocca-Serra, P.	Data to Metadata: Ensuring reproducibility in biomedical research, United Kingdom, 22 October 2020	2020
Research data alliance - RDA an organisation towards social and technical bridges to enable the open sharing and re-use of data with full credit to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data requirements ³⁶	Cambon-Thomsen, A., Mabile, L., Thomsen, M. & David, R.	JCAD 2019, Journées Calcul Données : Rencontres scientifiques et techniques du calcul et des données, Toulouse, France, 09-11 October 2019 (Poster session)	2019

3.2 Conferences and webinars FAIRplus partners attended

Table 6. List of conferences and webinar that FAIRplus partners attended and given presentation at

Event	Partners that delivered a talk	Topic of the talk	Date
M01-M18			
13th RDA Plenary meeting ³⁷	Anne Cambon-Thomsen and Laurence Mabile	n/a	2019-04-02
Semantics@Roche	Andrea Splendiani	n/a	2019-04-04
RESOLUTE Consortia General Assembly	Philip Gribbon	n/a	2019-05-06
2019 P-D-R Special Meeting on the FAIRification of External Data ³⁸	Tony Burdett, Phillipe Rocca-Serra	FAIR Perspectives: Academic Perspective	2019-05-21
	Herman Van Vlijmen	Overview of FAIRplus	

³⁵ <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4133822>

³⁶ https://zenodo.org/record/3479152#.Y01_AezMKFo

³⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rdas-13th-plenary-meeting-philadelphia-us>

³⁸ <https://www.p-d-r.com/resources/Documents/Press%20Release/2019-P-D-R-Special-Meeting-Agenda.pdf>

eTRANSafe Research Reproducibility Workshop ³⁹	Wei Gu	n/a	2019-06-04
ELIXIR All Hands 2019 ⁴⁰	Serena Scollen, Hannah Hurst	Plenary: Going beyond EXCELERATE	2019-06-20
GNA NOW Kick of Meeting	Philip Gribbon	n/a	2019-07-04
COMBINE EUSTANDS4PM Workshop	Carole Goble	n/a	2019-07-18
EOSC-Life 'FAIR Enough' Meeting ⁴¹	Jan-Willem Boiten	Workshop: Policies and Recommendations for the Processing of Sensitive Data	2019-09-04
Joint EOSC project meeting	Niklas Blomberg	n/a	2019-09-09
Journées annuelles RDA-France 2019 ⁴²	Laurence Mabile	Poster: Evaluation tool of FAIR criteria literacy and compliance to foster research data sharing.	2019-09-12
Open Science Fair 2019: Synergies for Sustainable, Open & Responsible Research ⁴³	Ebtisam Alharbi, Carole Goble, Caroline Jay	Poster: Understanding The Implications Of Implementing FAIR Data Principles In The Life Sciences	2019-09-16-18
CODATA 2019: Towards next-generation data-driven science: policies, practices and platforms ⁴⁴	Anne Cambon-Thomsen, Laurence Mabile	Session: The evidentiary time lag in introducing data intensive technologies in clinical practice.	2019-09-17
		Session: Expert views on evaluating data sharing efforts and	

³⁹ <https://etransafe.eu/etransafe-reproducibility-workshop/>

⁴⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-excelerate-all-hands-meeting-2019>

⁴¹ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/news/eosc-life-fair-enough-meeting-in-brussels/>

⁴² <https://rdafrance2019.sciencesconf.org/>

⁴³ <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/2019/all/index.php>

⁴⁴ https://conference.codata.org/conference/CODATA_2019/about/

		practices: an international dialogue fostered by an interest group of the research data alliance.	
		Poster: A European Project targeted at FAIR-ification tools, guidelines and processes for improving sharing data in the context of innovative medicine: FAIRplus	
		Poster: Evaluation tool of FAIR literacy to foster research data sharing.	
D4 Europe - Data-Driven Drug Development	Dorothy Reilly	n/a	2019-10-02
FORCE2019 annual meeting (Force11) ⁴⁵	Ebtisam Alharbi	Understanding the implications of implementing FAIR data principles in the life sciences	2019-10-16
14th RDA Plenary meeting ⁴⁶	Anne Cambon-Thomsen	n/a	2019-10-23
2019 AAPS PHARMSCI 360 ⁴⁷	Susanna-Assunta Sansone	FAIR Principles and Implementations in the Pharmaceutical Industry	2019-11-03
	Philippe Rocca-Serra	Experimental design-driven FAIRification of data matrices: example of a principled approach	

⁴⁵ <https://force2019.sched.com/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rdas-14th-plenary-helsinki-finland>

⁴⁷ <https://www.eventscribe.com/2019/PharmSci360/>

ELRIG Drug Discovery 2019 ⁴⁸	Philip Gribbon	Development of FAIR data methods in Life Science and Drug Discovery research	2019-11-05
		Session Chair: HIT FINDING STRATEGIES	
EOSC Symposium 2019 ⁴⁹	Oya Beyan	n/a	2019-11-25
BioData World Congress 2019	Andrea Splendiani	FAIR data panel	2019-12-04
Webinar: RDA FAIR data maturity model WG - Workshop #6 ⁵⁰	Nick Juty, Oya Beyan	n/a	2019-12-04
EuBOPEN Project meeting	Tony Burdett	n/a	2020-03-23
RDA 15th Plenary Meeting ⁵¹	Anne Cambon-Thomsen, Laurence Mabile	n/a	2020-05-06
Pistoia Alliance Webinar ⁵²	Philippe Rocca-Serra	SEMANTICS OF DATA MATRICES & THE STATO ONTOLOGY	2020-05-28
ELIXIR All Hands 2020 ⁵³	Fuqi Xu	'FAIRification for Knowledge Management' mini-symposium titled 'FAIRification in FAIRplus: From policy to practice'	2020-06-08
FAIRplus eTOX FAIRification to the eTRANSafe consortium	Laura Furlong, Vassilios Ioannidis, Francesco Ronzano	n/a	2020-06-15
Information meeting with IMI CARE project	Herman van Vlijmen	n/a	2020-06-18

⁴⁸ <https://www.elrig.org/portfolio/2019-drug-discovery/#1554901163582-fd2af15e-2706>

⁴⁹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium>

⁵⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg>

⁵¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-15th-plenary-meeting-australia>

⁵² <https://www.pistoiaalliance.org/pistoia-webinars/data-matrices-stato-ontology/>

⁵³ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-all-hands-2020>

M19-M36			
EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF)	Susanna Sansone	FAIR principles and their implementation	2020-09-02
	Anne Cambon-Thomsen	FAIR principles	
Future Labs	Oya Beyan	FAIR Capabilities	2020-09-28
UK Conference of Bioinformatics and Computational Biology 2020 ⁵⁴	Susanna Sansone	FAIRplus, tools and guidelines for making life science data FAIR	2020-09-29
D4 Global ⁵⁵	Oya Beyan	FAIR Maturity Pathways	2020-10-13
ELIXIR-CONVERGE WPLs TC	Oya Beyan	FAIR-CMM presentation to the CONVERGE WPLs	2020-10-13
GMDS workshop FAIR Data Infrastructures ⁵⁶	Carole Goble	FAIR Past, Present and Future	2020-10-15
EBI training, invited talk ⁵⁷	Fuqi Xu	Open with purpose: How and why to make your data open	2020-10-23
BioData Congress 2020 ⁵⁸	Oya Beyan	Using maturity models to support processes	2020-11-10
	Philippe Rocca-Serra	FAIRplus Cookbook	
International FAIR Convergence Symposium 2020 ⁵⁹	Tony Burdett, Philippe Rocca-Serra	Session Title: FAIR implementation by Life Science Industry - FAIRification of IMI datasets by FAIRplus ⁶⁰	2020-12-01
	Susanna Sansone	Q&A Panel Discussion	
Meeting with Scottish Government on	Alasdair Gray	n/a	2020-12-02

⁵⁴ <https://www.earlham.ac.uk/events/uk-conference-bioinformatics-and-computational-biology-2020#Programme-4>

⁵⁵ <https://www.d4-global.com/>

⁵⁶ <https://fairdomhub.org/events/228>

⁵⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/events/open-purpose-how-and-why-make-your-data-open/>

⁵⁸ <https://app.swapcard.com/event/biodata-world-congress-2020>

⁵⁹ <https://conference.codata.org/conference/FAIRconvergence2020/about/#>

⁶⁰ <https://conference.codata.org/FAIRconvergence2020/sessions/185/>

Corporate Data Repositories			
EFI (European Federation for Immunogenetics)	Anne Cambon Thomson	FAIRness and immunogenetics	2021-04-21- 2021-04-23
How FAIR Are You- CINECA Hackathon ⁶¹	Melanie Courtot, Fuqi Xu	Cohort FAIRification and FAIR assessment	2021-04-28
	Jolanda Strubel	How to measure FAIR. Experiences within FAIRplus	
FONDUE Datathon ⁶²	Fuqi Xu	BioSamples and plant data	2021-06-21
Oxford-Berlin Summer School	Susanna Sansone, Philippe Rocca-Serra	FAIR Principles and Implementations	2021-09-21- 2021-09-22
Open Science FAIR ⁶³	Susanna Sansone	FAIR Cookbook	2021-09-22
UK-CBCB conference ⁶⁴	Philippe Rocca-Serra	FAIR Cookbook	2021-09-28
EC workshop on COVID data and standards	Susanna Sansone	FAIR and relevant activities and examples	2021-10-11
Ontocommons project's workshop ⁶⁵	Philippe Rocca-Serra	FAIR Cookbook	2021-11-04
RDA Plenary 18th "Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations (HRPOs) WG" session ⁶⁶	Philippe Rocca-Serra	FAIR Cookbook	2021-11-03 & 2021-11-09
SWAT4HCLS conference 2022 ⁶⁷	Fuqi Xu	Features of a FAIR vocabulary	2022-01-12

⁶¹ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/news-events-all/how-fair-are-you-hackathon>

⁶² <https://github.com/PBR/elixir-fondue-datathon>

⁶³ <https://www.ontocommons.eu/news-events/events/applying-fair-principles-open-science-and-industry-drive-innovation-challenges>

⁶⁴ <https://www.earlham.ac.uk/uk-conference-bioinformatics-and-computational-biology-21#Day1-2>

⁶⁵ <https://ontocommons.eu/news-events/events/global-workshop-ontology-commons-addressing-challenges-industry-50-transition>

⁶⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-18th-plenary-meeting-virtual/wg-raising-fairness-health-data-and-health-research>

⁶⁷ <https://www.swat4ls.org/workshops/leiden2022/>

Festival of Genomics and Biodata	Jolanda Strubel	The FAIRplus project: FAIR put into practice	2022-01-25
M37-M48			
BioIT World Conference & Expo, Boston ⁶⁸	Nick Lynch	FAIR Implementation Challenges & Learnings	2022-05-03 - 2022-05-05
ELIXIR All Hands 2022 ⁶⁹	Hannah Hurst	FAIRplus All Hands Poster	2022-06-06 - 2022-06-10
1st Annual Symposium of the Knowledge Graphs IG at the Alan Turing Institute ⁷⁰	Susanna Sansone, Philippe Rocca-Serra	FAIR, community standards and data FAIRification: components and recipes	2022-06-16
International Data Week, Seoul 2022 ⁷¹	Ann-Kathrin Bernards	How to train future FAIR ambassadors	2022-06-22
RDA 19th Plenary (as a part of International Data Week 2022)	Anne Cambon-Thomsen	Poster: Ethical values in relation with Open Science and FAIR data principles in the EU project FAIRplus	2022-06-20 - 2022-06-22
MILA seminar ⁷²	Danielle Welter	Supporting FAIRness maturation with the FAIR Dataset Maturity model	2022-09-19
LCSB Biocore group meeting	Danielle Welter	Supporting FAIRness maturation with the FAIR Dataset Maturity model	2022-09-26
MAQC Society (Meeting with USA FDA) ⁷³	Susanna Sansone	"The FAIR Cookbook: pharma and academics join forces to make data FAIR"	2022-09-26 - 2022-09-27

⁶⁸ <https://www.bio-itworldexpo.com/22>

⁶⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-all-hands-2022>

⁷⁰ <https://github.com/turing-knowledge-graphs/meet-ups/blob/main/symposium-2022.md>

⁷¹ <https://idw2022.org/>

⁷² https://www.medizin.uni-greifswald.de/medizininformatik/news/singleview/?tx_ttnews%5Btt_news%5D=28&cHash=b56d97d9061e732d13f41a4d4bf0fd0c

⁷³ <https://themaqc.org/conferences/>

ESCMID/ASM Conference 2022 ⁷⁴	Yojana Gadiya, Rakel Arrazuria (COMBINE)	Poster presentation based on COMBINE-FAIRplus collaboration work: BPO: the Bioassay Protocol Ontology, a semantic approach to elevate the reusability of AMR-related drug discovery data	2022-10-04 - 2022-10-07
Semantics@Roche (Roche internal event)	Dorothy Reilly	IMI FAIRplus: developing FAIRification processes through collaboration	2022-10-05 - 2022-10-06
ELIXIR Programme TC	Serena Scollen	FAIRplus Update	2022-10-06
BioIT World Conference & Expo, Berlin ⁷⁵	Jan-Willem Boiten	Preparing Health Data for Secondary Use in Research & Innovation – Some Practical Use Cases	2022-10-18 - 2022-10-19
Global Summit on Regulatory Science (GSR22) ⁷⁶	Susanna Sansone	Open, FAIR and reproducible science	2022-10-19 - 2022-10-21
BioTechX (former BioData Congress)	Dorothy Reilly	IMI FAIRplus update: resources for doers, users, and contributors	2022-11-08 - 2022-11-10
EU-OPENSREEN Autumn school ⁷⁷	Philip Gribbon	Principles of open data an open source tools	2022-11-14

⁷⁴ https://www.escmid.org/dates_events/escmid_conferences/escmidasm_conference_2022

⁷⁵ <https://www.bio-itworldeurope.com/>

⁷⁶ <https://gcsr.net/2022-gsrs/>

⁷⁷ <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/training/autumn-training-school-2022.html>

4. Discussion

4.1 FAIRplus related Publications

For the duration of the FAIRplus project, there were 38 published FAIRplus-led and FAIRplus-related publications and 11 in-progress FAIRplus-led publications. For the FAIRplus-led publications, the project partners have published five FAIRplus-led publications in *Scientific Data* and *Drug Discovery Today*. The project partners are also preparing five more publications to be published and six more tentative publications are in preparation, which will be published after the end of the project.

As for the FAIRplus-related publications, there are seven publications based on the research co-funded by the FAIRplus project. These publications mostly focused on implementing the FAIR principles.

In total, there are 18 publications that cited the FAIRplus project, seven of them cited the FAIRplus project directly, two of them cited the FAIR Cookbook, and nine of them acknowledged funding from the FAIRplus project. Additionally, there are four publications that mentioned the FAIRplus project, including the FAIR Cookbook and the FAIRplus Fellowship Programme in the main text.

It is noticeable that both publications that cited the FAIR Cookbook ('Work Programme for Health for 2023-2024' and 'Maximising investments in health research: FAIR data for a coordinated COVID-19 response, workshop report') are published by the European Commission and both listed the FAIR Cookbook as a recommended guide for researchers to make their data FAIR.

Finally, there were four publications (presentations and posters) presented by the FAIRplus partners in meetings and conferences throughout the duration of the project.

4.2 Conferences and webinars FAIRplus partners attended

From M1 to M48 of the FAIRplus project, the project partners joined 63 events, including international conferences, webinars and workshops and internal meetings with collaborating projects. Some noticeable conferences that the partners participated and delivered presentations at include RDA plenary, ELIXIR All Hands, BioTechX (formerly known as BioData Congress) and International Data Week.

During these events, the FAIRplus partners presented 73 talks, workshops, plenary discussions and posters. The main purpose of these presentations was to demonstrate the achievements and outputs of the project. During the first reporting period (M1 to M18) of the project, most presentations focused on general discussion of the importance of FAIR principles and how they should be applied in life sciences academia as well as industry. Moving on to the second reporting period (M19-M36) of

the project, the partners had already developed standards, such as FAIR Data Maturity Model, and tools, such as the FAIR Cookbook. These outcomes were widely disseminated by the partners in different conferences. Finally, during the last reporting period (M37-M48) of the project, the presentations from project partners focused more on experience sharing, such as the FAIRplus Fellowship programme and FAIR Cookbook, and the sustainability of the project.

5. Conclusion

Under the FAIRplus project, five project-led publications have been published and there are eleven publications in progress. The outcomes of the FAIRplus project, including the FAIR Cookbook, FAIRplus Fellowship Programme and FAIR Principles, were also cited or mentioned in different publications. After the end of the project, these FAIRplus-led and FAIRplus-related publications can help sustain the project outcomes and continue to work as a guideline and reference to the FAIR principles and make research datasets FAIR.

The project partners also disseminated important outcomes of the project through delivering talks and presenting posters in meetings. These talks and posters presented by the FAIRplus partners are great examples of project experience sharing that can help the scientific community have a better understanding of the FAIR principles and tools available for FAIRifying their data.

Table 7. A summary of FAIRplus scientific publications

Publication type		Number
FAIRplus-led	Published	5
	In-progress	11
		16
FAIRplus-related	FAIRplus co-funded	7
	FAIRplus cited	7
	FAIR Cookbook cited	2
	FAIRplus funding cited	9
	FAIRplus mentioned (FAIR Cookbook/FAIRplus Fellowship Programme)	4
	FAIRplus presentations/posters	4

	33
Total	49